

A sensory-motor hand prosthesis with integrated thermal feedback

Authors

Jonathan Muheim^{1,*}, Francesco Iberite^{2,*}, Outman Akouissi^{1,3}, Rachel Monney¹, Federico Morosato⁴, Emanuele Gruppioni⁴, Silvestro Micera^{1,2,†,‡}, Solaiman Shokur^{1,†,‡}

1 Bertarelli Foundation Chair in Translational Neural Engineering, Neuro-X Institute, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.

2 The BioRobotics Institute, Health Interdisciplinary Center and Department of Excellence in Robotics and AI, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, 56127 Pisa, Italy.

3 Bertarelli Foundation Chair in Neuroprosthetic Technology, Neuro-X Institute, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.

4 Centro Protesi INAIL, 40054 Vigorso di Budrio, Italy.

Summary

Background Recently, we reported the presence of phantom thermal sensations in amputees: thermal stimulation of specific spots on the residual arm elicited thermal sensations in their missing hands. Here, we exploit phantom thermal sensations via a standalone system integrated into a robotic prosthetic hand to provide real-time and natural temperature feedback.

Methods The subject (male adult with unilateral transradial amputation) used the sensorized prosthesis to manipulate objects and distinguish their thermal properties. We tested his ability to discriminate between a) hot, cold, and ambient temperature objects, b) different materials (copper, glass, and plastic), and c) artificial versus human hands. We also introduced the thermal Box and Block Test (thermal BBT), a test to evaluate real-time temperature discrimination during standardized pick-and-place tasks.

Findings The subject performed all three discrimination tasks above chance level with similar accuracies as with his intact hand. Additionally, in all fifteen sessions of the thermal BBT, he correctly placed more than half of the samples. Finally, the phantom thermal sensation was stable during the thirteen recording sessions spread over 400 days.

Conclusion Our study paves the way for more natural hand prostheses that restore the full palette of sensations.

Funding

* Jonathan Muheim and Francesco Iberite contributed equally.

† Silvestro Micera and Solaiman Shokur contributed equally.

‡ Corresponding Authors: silvestro.micera@epfl.ch, solaiman.shokur@epfl.ch
Lead Contact: solaiman.shokur@epfl.ch

Bertarelli Foundation (including the Catalyst program); the Swiss National Science Foundation through the National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) Robotics; the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program; the Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme; the Ministry of University and Research (MUR), National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) and Tuscany Health Ecosystem.

Introduction

Recently, we showed that it is possible to deliver natural thermal sensations over the full range of non-painful stimuli (15°C to 40°C) in upper limb amputees. We reported that the noninvasive thermal stimulation of specific spots of the residual arm can induce phantom thermal sensations¹. We found that these sensations are stable over time and similar to the ones experienced on the intact arm. Building upon these findings, we developed a portable device called the MiniTouch that conveys real-time temperature feedback.

Here, we show the integration of the MiniTouch with a commercial RPH; we call this integrated standalone system the *Thermal prosthetic hand*. We show how a transradial amputee successfully exploited the Thermal prosthetic hand during a series of active sensory-motor tasks involving grasping, pinching, and poking to discriminate objects with different temperatures and materials and detect bodily contact. We also introduce a novel assessment protocol — the thermal Box Block Test — which evaluates the prosthetic user's ability to exploit the phantom thermal sensations in a real-time functional task.

Results

From thermal phantom sensations to the Thermal prosthetic hand

The subject (57-year-old male) has had a transradial amputation for 37 years with no phantom limb pain (VAS < 3); he participated in our previous study (participant P12)¹ and signed an informed consent form. The participant routinely used the MyoHand VariPlus (Ottobock, Germany). The procedure started with mapping the tactile and thermal phantom sensations using the thermal mapping protocol described by Iberite et al.¹ Using this protocol, we identified his thermal phantom hand maps, i.e., regions of the residual limb that can elicit thermal projected sensations.

Over the first 130 days, we performed four thermal mapping sessions; three points were consistently found to project into the phantom hand (see Fig. 1A). Then, on day 246, we selected one of these three stable points for the integration of the MiniTouch into the RPH; this point satisfied two critical conditions (a) its thermal projected sensation was stable (b) its location in the phantom hand map allowed the thermode to be placed without interfering with the EMG electrodes. We show in Fig 1B the placement of the thermode on the specific location on the phantom hand map and the sensor on the corresponding thermal projected spot on the prosthetic hand (index finger). Stable perpendicular contact of the thermode with the skin on the residuum

was achieved by using an adjustable frame. Following the integration, the participant used the Thermal prosthetic hand to perform various motor tasks over eight experimental sessions between days 247 and 413. No further adjustments of the thermode position were necessary during these experiments as the participant confirmed that his thermal projected sensation was maintained constant. Furthermore, the subject reported no difficulty using the EMG signals in controlling the Thermal prosthetic hand throughout the sessions, and no adverse effects were reported during the experiments.

Sensory-motor tasks

We first investigated whether the participant could discriminate three objects with different temperatures by grasping them. The subject was instructed to close the Thermal prosthetic hand on a bottle containing either cold water, water at ambient temperature, or hot water. All bottles were visually similar (no condensation, steam, etc.), and the experiment started with a 1-minute familiarization where the labels cold (20°C), ambient (24°C), and hot (40°C) were described. Three conditions were repeated ten times in a randomized order. Confirming that the participant could perceive the thermal differences of grasped objects, he reached 100% accuracy — the same score as when he used his intact hand. In contrast, validating that he only relied on the thermal information to perform the task, his accuracy dropped to 33% when the thermal feedback was turned off (Fig. 2A).

To investigate the detection of more subtle thermal differences, we presented three slabs of materials at room temperature in a random order (five repetitions per material). We used a piece of copper, glass, and plastic for this task, as previously tested by our group in healthy² and amputee¹ populations. The participant (blindfolded) used the Thermal prosthetic hand to pinch the slabs, and he responded to a forced-choice questionnaire. The participant was correct in 67% of the cases, with no confusion between the plastic and copper conditions; his accuracy rate was comparable to the one found when he used his intact arm to touch the objects (67% and chance level with $p < 0.01 = 60%$) (Fig. 2B). Once again when the thermal feedback was turned off, his accuracy did not exceed chance level.

While detecting objects' temperature and material is interesting to increase the catalog of thermal sensations for prosthetic users, an even more important aspect is to detect bodily sensations to potentially facilitate interactions with others. This was spontaneously reported several times by participants from our previous study. One participant said: "*The most impressive for me was when the experimenter placed the sensor on his own body. [...] I could feel the warmth of another person with my phantom hand. It [was] like having a connection with someone.*" To further investigate this crucial feature, we checked whether the participant (blindfolded) could discriminate a human arm from a prosthetic one by poking it. As a control, and because the compliance of a prosthetic hand could be different from a human hand, we also tested a softer silicone hand. We presented four conditions: two artificial arms (one prosthetic and one rubber arm) and two real arms (one female and one male subject). The participant poked the arm with his prosthetic hand for 5 seconds and reported whether it was a human arm or an artificial one. The participant detected correctly in 80% of the trials when the thermal feedback was On, a rate below the one reached with the intact hand (100%) but significantly above the chance level (chance level with $p < 0.01 =$

75%). The detection accuracy was 60% when the thermal feedback was off; therefore, while compliance might play some role in detecting the different artificial limbs, the thermal feedback boosted the detection accuracy (Fig. 2C).

Finally, we introduced a novel test to assess thermal feedback in a motor task. We based our assessment on the standard box and block test (BBT)³, where the participant has to move as many cubes as possible from one box to another in one minute.

Adding to the difficulty, in our test – called the thermal BBT – the cubes (made of stainless steel) were either cold (20°C) or hot (40°C), and the participant had to store them in a red (hot) or blue (cold) zone (Supplementary Movie S1). We repeated the thermal BBT 30 times: 15 with the thermal feedback On and 15 with the thermal feedback Off in a randomized order.

To confirm that the participant was familiar with the task and was able to move the blocks with the thermal prosthetic hand, we also performed ten standard BBT sessions in standard conditions (cubes were at room temperature and thermal feedback was Off); the participant was able to move between 23 and 32 cubes/minute. Comparatively, when considering the Thermal BBT task, the participant moved on average 10.2 ± 1.1 blocks/minute for the feedback On and 13.9 ± 2.8 for the Feedback Off session (mean \pm SD). The decrease in the number of blocks in the thermal BBT compared to the standard BBT can be easily understood: the participant had to do a thermal discrimination task while performing the pick and place.

Crucially, when considering the feedback On session, we found that the participant correctly placed more than half of the blocks in *all* 15 sessions (min score = 64%). Overall, the participant correctly placed 114 out of 153 moved blocks. His error rates for hot and cold blocks were similar (22 errors over 76 hot blocks and 17 over 77 cold blocks). The participant was significantly worse at performing the task when the thermal feedback was Off (means accuracy for feedback On = 75%, feedback Off = 50%, $p < 0.001$, Wilcoxon rank-sum test). This test confirmed that the participant could perform a motor task with quick thermal discrimination. We believe the thermal BBT can become a benchmark test for the future development of RPH with thermal feedback.

Discussion

We showed a novel sensory-motor prosthetic hand with integrated thermal feedback and its validation with a transradial amputee. Three important observations can be made: (a) the participant could control the Thermal prosthetic hand to actively explore objects to detect their thermal properties, (b) we found the presence of stable phantom thermal sensations in 413 days, (c) no adverse events were registered during any of the experiments. The participant's accuracy level when using the Thermal prosthetic hand to discriminate different objects' temperatures and materials was similar to the one with his intact hand. On the other hand, for the detection of bodily contact, while the presence of thermal feedback was found to improve the detection rate, it did not reach one of the intact hand, probably due to the lack of other multisensory information, such as skin texture.

Considering our previous finding that thermal phantom sensations are prevalent in upper limb amputees¹ and the rather simplicity of the Thermal prosthetic hand, which necessitates no surgical intervention, uses off-the-shelf electronics, and can be personalized in just a few

sessions, we believe our solution has the potential to become widespread for prosthetic users. Nevertheless, challenges lie ahead. First, further miniaturization of the controller and heat extraction module is necessary to integrate the thermal controller *inside* the socket (particularly challenging when the residual arm is long). Next, integrating multiple thermodes would be necessary for evoking larger parts of the phantom hand. Also, while no adverse effects were observed during both the current and our previous study¹, we need to carefully characterize the thermal feedback in all sorts of external conditions and its long-term effects.

But these challenges are worth the effort as the long-term use of the Thermal prosthetic hand could open completely new perspectives for prosthetic users. First, the participants could gather new sensations, such as wetness and richer bodily sensations. Second, for the first time, we can envision the possibility of restoring a multimodal palette of natural sensations integrating the thermal phantom sensations with tactile feedback via noninvasive⁴ or invasive⁵ interfaces. This could promote social interaction and affective touch^{6,7}; a particularly interesting implementation of such technology might be for bilateral amputees.

Third, while in the current work, we mainly concentrated on the active discrimination of thermal features of external objects, thermal feedback is also an interoceptive sensation: we can, for example, feel that our hands are cold or hot even when we touch nothing. An open question is how an interoceptive phantom thermal sensation influences RPH users' perception and how it could possibly boost their embodiment. Finally, knowing that integrating sensory feedback in RPH reduces phantom limb pain^{8,9}, we believe there is an opportunity for using thermal feedback to this end. Our case study shows the tremendous potential of the thermal prosthetic hand for clinical applications and opens the way for the investigation of the long-term term effects of thermal feedback on patients' quality of life.

Limitations of Study

The current work was a case study with a single transradial amputee; further studies with a larger cohort are necessary to confirm that more patients can use the thermal prosthetic hand. A second limitation is that the tests were done under controlled conditions; the possible influence of external factors such as air temperature and humidity and subject-related factors such as body temperature have not been considered.

Acknowledgment

We thank R. Ramos García, M. Sayar, and I. Furfaro for their valuable help. We also thank Dr. Bassolino for her insightful feedback. We thank S. Dalmiani, F. Migliarese, and the Centro Protesi Inail for their contribution to the customization of the socket and assembly of the final device. We thank the subject who freely donated his time to the study.

This work was supported by the Bertarelli Foundation (including the Catalyst program); the Swiss National Science Foundation through the National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) Robotics and the CHRONOS project; and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant 754354. This work was also supported by the Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme under grant 101092612 (Social and hUman ceNtered XR - SUN project), the #NEXTGENERATIONEU (NGEU) and partially funded by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR), National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) with two projects: MNESYS (PE0000006)–A Multiscale integrated approach to the study of the nervous system in health and disease (DN. 1553 11.10.2022) and THE (IECS00000017)–Tuscany Health Ecosystem (DN.1553 11.10.2022).

Authors contributions

Conceptualization: J.M., F.I., E.G., S.M. and S.S. Data collection: J.M., F.I., F.M. and S.S. Data analysis: J.M., F.I., S.M. and S.S. Development of the Thermal prosthetic hand: J.M., O.A., R.M., S.M. and S.S. Supervision: S.M. and S.S. Writing – original draft: J.M., F.I., S.M. and S.S. Writing – review & editing: All authors. J.M., F.I., S.M., and S.S. had unrestricted access to all data. All authors read and approved the final article and take responsibility for its content.

Declaration of interests:

S.M. holds shares in SensArs, which aims to develop bionic limbs for amputees. F.I., J.M., O.A., S.M., and S.S. are coinventors of a thermal sensing device and sensory feedback system and method using said thermal sensing device.

Inclusion and diversity

We support inclusive, diverse, and equitable conduct of research.

Main figure titles and legends

Figure 1. Integration of the thermal feedback system with a commercial RPH.

(A) Protocol timeline, including the thermal mapping of the residual arm and the experiments with the integrated Thermal prosthetic hand. A precise map of the residual arm was done using a thermode. We tested three temperatures: baseline skin temperature (32°C), below (25°C) and above (37°C) skin baseline. Three stable thermal projected spots were found between day one and day 130; among them, the blue point was chosen for integrating the MiniTouch with the RPH of the participant. The blue spot was then used between days 247 and 413 for a series of experiments with the Thermal prosthetic hand. During all these sessions, both skin baseline, below and above skin baseline stimulation elicited consistent thermal phantom sensations in the missing index finger. **(B)** The MiniTouch system integrates three main elements. (1) The Active Thermal Skin (ATS) sensor is a thin-film sensor integrating a heating track that stabilizes the sensor baseline temperature to 32°C and a sensing track monitoring the contact temperature. (2) The housing contains the system controller and a rechargeable battery. (3) The thermal display comprises a thermoelectric module, a temperature sensor, and a heatsink. It conveys the temperature of the ATS sensor on the thermal phantom spot. The support of the thermal display is mounted on screws ensuring that the thermode stays in tight contact with the skin. Top to down: the position of the projected thermal spots and the placement of the EMG sensors on the residual arm; the blue spot was selected as it did not interfere with the EMG electrodes. Square sections of the inner (2x2 cm²) and outer (4.2x4.2 cm²) sockets were carved to accommodate the thermode.

Figure 2. Participant performance in sensory-motor tasks.

(A) Confusion matrices for three-class forced-choice identification of bottles of water with cold (20°C), ambient (24°C), or hot (40°C). **(B)** Confusion matrix for three-class forced-choice identification of copper, glass, or plastic slabs at ambient temperature (24°C). **(C)** Identification of artificial and human arms when poking a stiff prosthetic hand (PH), a soft rubber hand (RH), and two subjects' arms (S1 and S2). For panels (A) to (C), we report the scores when the participant used the thermal prosthetic hand with the thermal feedback On or Off and when he used the index finger of his non-amputated hand (intact index). **(D)** (Left) Confusion matrix (number of moved

blocks over 15 sessions) and (Right) Classification accuracy (correctly placed blocks, mean \pm SD) for the thermal BBT with the thermal feedback turned On or Off.

STAR Methods text

Key resources table

REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Software and Algorithms		
MATLAB R2023a and Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox		https://ch.mathworks.com/

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contacts, Silvestro Micera (silvestro.micera@epfl.ch) and Solaiman Shokur (solaiman.shokur@epfl.ch).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique reagents.

Data and code availability

- All data reported in this paper will be shared by the lead contact upon request.
- This paper does not report original code.
- Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead contact upon request.

Experimental model and study participant details

The subject (57-year-old male) has had a transradial amputation for 37 years with no phantom limb pain (VAS < 3). Overall, we ran 13 sessions with the participant (four were described in Iberite et al. ¹) over 414 days. Sessions typically ranged between 2 and 6 hours with breaks.

The participant signed an informed consent form. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Emilia Area of the Center of the Emilia-Romagna Region (CE-AVEC) (protocol CP-PRO-02-20).

Method details

We ran four sets of experiments with the MiniTouch mounted on the user's prosthetic hand. After describing the mounting of the MiniTouch on the prosthesis, we will detail the corresponding setup, protocol, familiarization, and testing phase for each experiment.

Mounting the MiniTouch on a prosthesis

Here, we describe the step-by-step procedure to mount the MiniTouch on the user's prosthesis. First, the socket was adapted to arrange the MiniTouch thermode. The inner socket and the robotic prosthetic hand were disassembled from the outer socket. The thermal phantom spot was first detected based on the thermal mapping protocol described in ¹, and it was marked with a skin marker on the residual arm. The participant was asked to fit the inner socket. This inner socket being transparent, the opening for the Peltier was precisely marked and next cut out (20x20 mm²). A larger cut-out (42x42 mm²), adjusted to the thermode frame dimensions, was then made in the outer socket. Four holes were drilled, and plastic M4 screws were fixed with epoxy adhesive. Then, the ATS sensor was placed on the prosthesis finger. A latex finger glove was mounted on the Robotic Prosthetic Hand (RPH) finger. This finger glove was meant to avoid direct fixation of the ATS sensor on the participant's everyday life RPH glove. To have congruent thermal and visual feedback (i.e., the referred sensation elicited by the thermode on the residual arm projected to the area of the RPH in contact with the object), the ATS sensor was fixed on the prosthesis index fingertip with double-sided tape.

Finally, the housing containing the temperature controller and battery was fastened on the socket with Velcro and elastic bands. It was placed on the lateral side of the socket so as not to interfere during movements.

Temperature Discrimination Experiment

Setup

Three identical brown glass bottles of 7 cm in body diameter and 27 cm in height were used (approx. 550 mL content). The three stimuli were chosen to illustrate interacting with surrounding objects: one cold, one hot, and one at ambient temperature (24°C). The water in the bottle for the cold condition was set around 12°C, which was below the MiniTouch saturation temperature (20°C); this ensured the subject always received 20°C stimulation even if the water warmed up during the experiment. The same was true for the hot stimulation saturated at 40°C and when the water in the bottle was set well above. To avoid any visual cue that could help classify the bottles, we carefully dried them and filled them entirely to eliminate any possible condensation or steam.

Protocol

The participant was seated and not blindfolded during the experiment. The bottles were handled by the experimenter holding the bottleneck with thermally insulating neoprene gloves. Every repetition starts with the participant having his robotic prosthesis hand open. The experimenter approaches the bottle and asks the participant to close the hand, keep it closed for 5 seconds and report the temperature of stimuli using a force choice questionnaire 'cold', 'ambient', or 'hot'.

Familiarization phase: As a first step, to make sure that the ATS is correctly mounted and that the participant is comfortable with the stimuli temperatures, the three bottles are successively presented. For each of them, the experimenter orally announces the label in Italian, the participant's mother tongue, prior to giving the instruction to close the hand. The exact phrasing is: "Questo è freddo/ambiente/caldo" ("This is cold/ambient/hot"). During this phase, the participant spontaneously reported feeling a clear cold/hot sensation on the phantom hand for the extreme bottles and a "barely barely cold" sensation ("apena appena freddo") for the ambient temperature one. This comment is in line with both the light temperature drop from the baseline measured by the ATS sensor when in contact with the ambient temperature bottle and the phenomenological experience of touching objects at ambient temperature (24°C).

Test phase: The three bottles were presented 10 times in a randomized sequence (30 trials). A 3-minute break was given after half of the trials. Figure S1A shows the ATS sensor and thermode temperatures during the entire duration of the test. The positive peak after 950 seconds was due to a faulty contact of the ATS sensor connector, which was manually restored. The thermal display setpoint was kept in a non-painful range (20-40°C) by saturating the ATS sensor measurement. It can be seen that the thermal display for the hot and cold were consistently at 40 and 20°C throughout the test. The overshoot of the PID controller did not exceed 42°C.

We proceeded with a similar protocol for the test with the intact hand. This time, cold water at 20°C and hot water at 40°C were used for the extreme bottles, which correspond to the stimuli temperatures with the thermode. The participant was asked to pinch the bottle between the index and the thumb of the intact hand for 5 seconds.

Material Discrimination Experiment

Setup

In this experiment, three identical copies were used for each material (copper, glass, plastic). The materials were cut into 4x4 cm slabs of 3mm thickness. The plastic slabs were made of Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). The three copies of each material were successively used in order to avoid heating up the slabs over time. Additionally, the experimenter manipulated the materials with insulating neoprene gloves to avoid body heat transfer. The participant was blindfolded with his robotic prosthetic hand in a comfortable position, resting on the table. The participant was asked to lay the prosthesis on the table to avoid feeling the weight of the slabs.

Protocol

For each trial, the experimenter made sure that the ATS sensor stabilized to a temperature close to the participant baseline level (on average 31.5°C). To speed up this process, the experimenter momentarily touched the ATS sensor with his forearm. Then, the experimenter placed the next material between the prosthesis index and thumb and gave instructions to close the robotic hand. After 8 seconds, the participant opened the hand and orally reported the identified material.

Familiarization phase: Before starting the test, the materials were presented in sequence: copper, glass and plastic. The experimenter announced the new material ("Questo è rame/vetro/plastica", "This is copper/glass/plastic") and then asked to close the hand. After the three materials were presented, the participant confirmed that he could perceive a subtle difference in the stimuli but that it was a "difficult task". The same procedure was followed in the two other conditions. In the case where the thermal feedback was turned off, the participant reported that he did not feel any sensation when touching the slabs. For the repetition of the test with the intact hand, the participant used his left index to touch the material slab placed on the table. The experimenter firmly held the slabs into place and made sure that the participant only moved his index vertically.

Test phase: During the test, the materials were presented 5 times in a randomized sequence (15 trials in total). The experiment lasted approximately 10 minutes for each condition. Figure S1B shows the temperature drops elicited by the contact with the materials during the experiment (in the thermal feedback On condition).

Bodily Contact Experiment

Setup

In this experiment, the blindfolded participant had to identify whether he was touching a natural or an artificial hand. Four different samples were possible: a hard robotic prosthetic hand, a soft rubber hand, and the forearm of two subjects (one male and one female) (Figure S2A). The participant was standing in front of a table on which the prosthetic hand, the rubber hand or the subjects' forearm were placed. The samples were firmly held in place by the experimenter to avoid movement when touched. The contact with the artificial hands was on the back of the hand, which presented the widest uniform surface. The natural arms were touched in the middle of the forearm (ventral part).

Protocol

The experimenter guided the Thermal prosthetic hand a few centimeters above the samples and let the participant lower the hand. The participant was instructed to perform only vertical indentation of the samples (poking). He was allowed to freely repeat the indentation phase for the whole duration the sample was presented. After five seconds, he lifted the hand and orally reported whether he believed it was an artificial or natural hand.

Familiarization phase: Each sample was presented one time before the testing phase. The experimenter orally announced the label of the sample (artificial or natural) and instructed the participant to poke it with the Thermal prosthetic hand.

Test phase: The test phase consisted of 20 trials (5 times each sample in a random sequence). Between each trial, the experimenter ensured that the ATS sensor had returned to the baseline temperature. The test was repeated for the thermal feedback Off condition and with the intact hand. In this case, the participant used his index finger to poke the samples.

Thermal Box and Block Test

We propose a novel test based on the Box and Block test (BBT). The BBT is a functional test to evaluate manual dexterity¹⁰. It consists of a "pick up" box and a "target" box separated by a central partition. In 60 seconds, the participant has to move, with one hand, as many blocks as possible from the pick-up to the target box. The number of blocks moved is used to assess the participant's gross manual dexterity. Here, we propose a thermal version of this test to illustrate the sensory-motor capabilities of the participant wearing the Thermal prosthetic hand. The pick-up box contains visually identical hot and cold cubes. In addition to moving the blocks from one box to the other, the participant has to classify them by placing them in a red (hot) or blue (cold) zone.

Setup

We fabricated a custom version of the box based on the standard BBT. Having the same dimensions as the standard BBT (Figure S2B), the only difference lies in the absence of the front and side walls. Only the wall closer to the participant's body was kept as we noticed that it could make picking up some blocks slightly harder. The box is made of 5mm thick MDF boards that were laser cut and 3D printed PLA joints that allow easy mounting and dismounting of the setup. A total of 32 pieces of 25x25x25mm stainless steel "whisky ice cubes" (Rosenstein & Söhne) were used. In the thermal version of the test, the target compartment was divided longitudinally into two equal zones by placing a printed paper sheet: red for hot blocks (closer to the separation) and blue for cold blocks.

In order to keep the hot and cold blocks visually identical, the cubes have to be dry to avoid condensation or steam. To maintain the correct temperature on all blocks, we placed the cubes in a resealable plastic (IKEA ISTAD) immersed in a 3.3 l jar filled with water. The temperature of the water was approximately 12°C (for cold blocks) and 45°C (hot blocks). Once again, the ATS sensor measurement was saturated between 20 and 40°C. The experimenter used heat-insulating neoprene gloves to manipulate the blocks.

The thermal BBT sessions were performed either with the thermal feedback On or Off. Additionally, the standard BBT was also repeated as a baseline measurement of the participant's motor-only capabilities. In all cases, the participant wore the same Thermal prosthetic hand. In the case of the standard BBT, the colored separation in the target compartment was removed. The classification accuracy was checked at the end of the test with a thermal camera (Teledyne FLIR 300).

Protocol

Familiarization Phase: Before the first test, a familiarization phase with 4 blocks (2 hot and 2 cold) was performed. The participant did not have any time constraints to move and classify the blocks. During this phase, the temperature measured by the ATS sensor was monitored in order to ensure the proper placement of the ATS on the prosthesis index fingertip. He confirmed that he could feel the temperature differences and correctly classified them in the target compartment.

Test Phase: The tests were repeated 15 times for the thermal BBT (15 times feedback On and 15 times feedback OFF). We also ran 10 times for the standard version to confirm that the participant was familiar with the task and was able to move the blocks with the thermal prosthetic hand. Each thermal BBT test started with the participant standing in front of the setup. For the thermal BBT, the exact phrasing of the instruction was: "In 60 seconds, move as many blocks as you can and place the blocks you feel as hot in the red zone and the ones you feel as cold in the blue zone." The test started when the experimenter dropped four blocks in the pick-up box. The first initial blocks consisted of 2 hot and 2 cold cubes. Once all blocks were moved, the experimenter placed 4 new blocks in the pick-up zone. The combination of hot/cold cubes was randomly alternated among the following combinations: 2 hot/2 cold, 3 hot/1 cold and 1 hot/3 cold. For the standard test, the participant was only instructed to "move as many cubes as possible into the target compartment".

Quantification and statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with MATLAB R2023a and Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox. The number of repetitions (n) is reported in the text. When checking the statistical significance of classification tests, we used the method described by Combrisson and colleagues¹¹ with $p < 0.01$. For the comparison between classification accuracy in thermal BBT we used a non-parametric method (Wilcoxon rank-sum test).

Supplemental video

Supplementary Movie S1. Thermal Box and Block Test, related to Fig. 2D. The participant uses the Thermal prosthetic hand to move and separate as many hot (40°C) and cold (20°C) metal cubes as possible in 60 seconds.

References

1. Iberite, F., Muheim, J., Akouissi, O., Gallo, S., Rognini, G., Morosato, F., Clerc, A., Kalff, M., Gruppioni, E., Micera, S., et al. (2023). Restoration of natural thermal sensation in upper-limb amputees.
2. Kalff, M.N., Shokur, S., Lavado, E.F., and Micera, S. (2021). Material surface detection on various body parts: A preliminary study for temperature substitution for upper arm amputees. *International IEEE/EMBS Conference on Neural Engineering, NER 2021-May*, 195–198. 10.1109/NER49283.2021.9441262.
3. Mathiowetz, V., Volland, G., Kashman, N., and Weber, K. (1985). Adult norms for the Box and Block Test of manual dexterity. *Am J Occup Ther.* 10.5014/ajot.39.6.386.
4. Hao, M., Chou, C.H., Zhang, J., Yang, F., Cao, C., Yin, P., Liang, W., Niu, C.M., and Lan, N. (2020). Restoring finger-specific sensory feedback for transradial amputees via non-invasive evoked tactile sensation. *IEEE Open J Eng Med Biol* 1. 10.1109/OJEMB.2020.2981566.
5. Raspopovic, S. (2020). Advancing limb neural prostheses. *Science* (1979) 370. 10.1126/science.abb1073.
6. Ackerley, R., Backlund Wasling, H., Liljencrantz, J., Olausson, H., Johnson, R.D., and Wessberg, J. (2014). Human C-Tactile Afferents Are Tuned to the Temperature of a Skin- Stroking Caress. *Journal of Neuroscience* 34, 2879–2883. 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2847-13.2014.
7. McGlone, F., Wessberg, J., and Olausson, H. (2014). Discriminative and Affective Touch: Sensing and Feeling. Preprint, 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.05.001 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.05.001.
8. Dietrich, C., Walter-Walsh, K., Preißler, S., Hofmann, G.O., Witte, O.W., Miltner, W.H.R., and Weiss, T. (2012). Sensory feedback prosthesis reduces phantom limb pain: Proof of a principle. Preprint, 10.1016/j.neulet.2011.10.068 10.1016/j.neulet.2011.10.068.
9. Petrini, F.M., Bumbasirevic, M., Valle, G., Ilic, V., Mijović, P., Čvančara, P., Barberi, F., Katic, N., Bortolotti, D., Andreu, D., et al. (2019). Sensory feedback restoration in leg amputees improves walking speed, metabolic cost and phantom pain. *Nat Med* 25, 1356–1363. 10.1038/s41591-019-0567-3.
10. Desrosiers, J., Bravo, G., Hébert, R., Dutil, É., and Mercier, L. (1994). Validation of the Box and Block Test as a measure of dexterity of elderly people: Reliability, validity, and norms studies. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil* 75. 10.1016/0003-9993(94)90130-9.
11. Combrisson, E., and Jerbi, K. (2015). Exceeding chance level by chance: The caveat of theoretical chance levels in brain signal classification and statistical assessment of decoding accuracy. *J Neurosci Methods* 250, 126–136. 10.1016/J.JNEUMETH.2015.01.010.